

XY-8 Pyrolysis Plant Main Parts & Specifications

Name	Photo	Specifications	Qty
1. pyrolysis process system			
Reactor (full open door)		capacity: 4-5MT/Batch 8-10MT/Batch power:7.5kw Size: Φ2200*6000*16 Φ2600*6600*16 Weight: 7MT/10MT material:Q245R Rpm:0.4R/M Drive:reducer EX-Motor Accessories:safety valves, packings, Aluminum packing, etc.	1 Set
2. Carbon black discharging system			
discharging screw		6 meters long, water outside of screw,can cooling the carbon. More clean and advanced.	1 Set
3. Cooling System			
Gas separator		Gas separator : Size : Φ800 *2000mm Working pressure:<3000Pa Working Temp.: 320°C Thickness: 4.5mm Heavy fuel oil storage tank :Φ600*1500mm Thickness: 3.5mm	1 Set
condenser (Option)		Size:Φ2750*6500*2250 Thickness:3.5mm Mat.:Q235 Weight:3Tons/piece Work pre.:<0.025Mpa Water inlet temp:<28°C Outlet temp.:<38°C	1 set

oil tank		Volume:5m ³ Size:Φ1200*3000mm Material:Q235 Thickness:3.5mm Weight:400kg Work pre.:<0.025Mpa Working temp.:38°C Accessories: view-glass, Flange, Compensator.	1 set
Oil pump		Flow speed:80L/min Weight: 18kg Working pressure: <0.33Mpa Working Temp:<38°C Tyre:Gear pump Anti-explosion motor:2.2kw	1 Set
Cooling Tower		Flow speed:50m ³ Working pressure: <0.6Mpa Working temp.:<35°C Type: Round Countercurrent flow Motor:3.0kw	1 Set
4. waste gas recycling system			
Waste gas recycling system		Size:Φ900*1800mm Material:Q235 Thickness:3.5mm Weight: 300kg Work pre.:<0.025Mpa Working temp.:<40°C Accessories:safe valve, Flange, ball valve, ETC.	1 Set
Waste gas burners		Capacity:25m ³ /h Process: waste gas	4 pieces
5. Smoke scrubber system			
Smoke Scrubbers (option)		Capacity:<4500m ³ /h Size:Φ1000*3200 Type:spray Material:Q235 Thickness:5.0mm Weight:350kg Accessories: smoke flue, fillers etc	2-3 pieces

Draft fan		Flow speed: 4750-7650m ³ /h Pressure:1697-4297pa Type:centrifugal Temp.:<350°C Material:304 Motor:4.0kw	1 piece
Recycle water pump		Flow speed: 20m ³ /h Lift:15m Working Temp.: <350°C Material:Q235 Motor:1.5kw	1 Set
6. Heating system			
Burning room		Size:2800*2500*1800 Heat:500,000kj/h Working Temp.:1100°C Material: anti-fire bricks and cement. Fuel:Coal, wood, or carbon black pallet and the sync gas Note:materials supplied by buyer, will be done in site.	1 Set
Natural gas burner Or Oil burner		Consumption: 25-50m ³ /h Fuel:Natural gas Heat output: 900-1800 MJ/h Consumption: 35kg/h Fuel:oil	1 Set
Blowers		Flow speed: 1330-1700m ³ /h Pre.:1697-4297pa Type:centrifugal Working Temp.:<80°C Material:Q235 Motor:4.0kw	2 pieces
7. Controlling system			
Controller		common traditional controller; option: PLC controller	1 Set